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A PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF TAKAFUL AND CONVENTIONAL INSURANCE IN BAHRAIN

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Abstract:

This research paper measures the efficiency of life insurance industry in Bahrain. While the major focus of this study is to compare the performance of takaful operators in comparison to conventional insurance during the period of 2009 to 2012. An in-depth review of available literature was undertaken to gather sufficient relevant data to accomplish the purpose. The data has been collected from different secondary sources like reports and papers etc. The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method has been used to examine the efficiency of life insurance industry in Bahrain with respect to takaful operators in comparison to conventional insurance. Finally, on the basis of the above analysis, the challenges and opportunities before the life insurance industry in Bahrain has been sketched out.

Keywords: Takaful, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), Bahrain.

Introduction:

The birth of insurance industry in Bahrain started from 1950, when a group of taxi drivers gathered to form an insurance society, the first mutual insurance company of its kind, in order to abide by the law to buy Third Party Liability insurance cover for their vehicles. This society was so successful that by 1955

the Co-operative Compensation Society was formed to provide insurance for vehicles and other losses arising from accidents. This society was later renamed as the Vehicle Insurance Fund.(Insurance Market review-2012-CBB)

The first organisation to be granted a license to offer long-term insurance products (life and accident insurance) in the Kingdom was American Life Insurance Company (ALICO), which commenced its operations in 1961. ALICO started to launch the first life protection, savings and personnel accident schemes for individuals and corporates in Bahrain.

Bahrain Insurance Company (BIC) was the first public shareholding company and was established on 2nd November 1969, even before the enactment of the Commercial Companies Law promulgated by Decree No. (28) of 1975. The company was incorporated with a paid up capital of BD 600,000, one third of the Paid up share capital owned by General Organization for Insurance, an Iraqi insurance company. BIC was later merged (in 1999) with National Insurance Company (established in 1982) to form Bahrain National Holding (BNH) Company.

Bahrain Islamic Insurance Company (BIIC), now called Takaful International Company, is the first Islamic insurance company to be incorporated in the Kingdom in 1989. As one of the early players in the Islamic financial field, BIIC offered Islamic insurance products and services which were designed to meet the increasing demand for such products. The Takaful industry has grown over the years and there are now seven Takaful and two Retakaful companies operating in Bahrain.

The study of comparative performance analysis of insurance industry is important for dual financial system in Bahrain where the takaful operators are operating in parallel to the conventional insurance companies. These study examine efficiency of insurance industry for the period 2009-2012 and compares the performance of takaful companies with their conventional counterparts (conventional insurance companies) in Bahrain.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The main focus of current study is to compare the performance of *takaful* operators in comparison to conventional insurance during the period of 2009 to 2012.

For this purpose, all the life insurance companies in Bahrain were analysed on the basis of the sources of efficiency and technical changes. A non-parametric approach of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) together with Malmquist Index was used to segregate the contributions of technical change, efficiency change, the pure and scale changes to total factor productivity growth of different takaful and conventional insurance companies in Bahrain.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The primary objectives of the study are:

- To understand the concept of *takaful* (*Islamic Life Insurance*) in comparison to conventional insurance.
- To measure the efficiency of life insurance industry in Bahrain
- To compare the performances of *takaful* operators in comparison to conventional insurance in Bahrain.
- To Sketch out the challenges and opportunities before the life insurance industry in Bahrain

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Earlier review showed that there were a fewer studies conducted measuring the efficiency of life insurance industry. But there was no of the past studies conducted particularly in Bahrain perspective that had taken all of the insurance companies in Bahrain to measure the efficiency of insurance industry and for comparative analysis between *akaful* operators and conventional insurance during the period of 2009 to 2012. The current study adds to the already existing research literature and explores important implications for the insurance operators who are always working to improve operating performance and to enhance the effectiveness of the monetary system as a whole.

The insurance sector in Bahrain:

Bahrain has exclusive social, political and economic structures that fix to set it apart from other Arab oil-producing Gulf States. There is mainly two types of insurance in the Middle East are conventional insurance and Islamic insurance. In recent times, the Bahraini insurance industry has been showing strong and steady growth. Total Gross Premiums written in 2007 was BD 140.09 million that saw growth of 34% to register BD 187.05 million in 2008. The Insurance industry continued to grow by around 9% to register BD 239.05 million in 2012 in comparison to Total Gross Premiums was BD 218.66 million in 2011.

Many international insurers have chosen Bahrain as their regional base for developing their Middle-East operations. There are 26 locally incorporated firms and 11 Overseas Insurance Firms (branches of foreign companies) carrying out insurance business in the Kingdom of Bahrain. (CBB: Insurance Market Review 2012).

Takaful Firms operating in Bahrain have risen significantly over the course of the last ten years. Takaful firms' gross contributions reached BD 53.67 million in 2012 compared to BD 43.91 million in 2011, an increase of around 22%. While Takaful firms' gross contributions in 2007 was BD 15.7 million. (CBB: Insurance Market Review 2008, CBB: Insurance Market Review 2012).

Table 1: Summary of Insurance Firms and Organisations Authorised in Bahrain (2003 - 2012)

Name of Insurance Firms/Organisation	2012	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007	2006	2005	2004	2003
Bahraini Insurance Firms	26	27	27	27	25	22	19	12	12	12
Overseas Branches) Insurance Firms (Foreign	11	11	11	11	11	11	9	8	9	9
Insurance Operation Outside Licensees Bahrain Limited to Representative Offices	33	37	41	46	46	53	56	60	73	84
Insurance Brokers	5	5	5	5	6	6	5	6	7	7
Insurance Consultants	31	33	33	32	32	33	33	30	29	25
Loss Adjusters	5	5	5	4	4	5	7	7	7	7
Actuaries	11	11	11	11	12	10	9	9	8	8
Insurance Pools & Syndicates	30	27	25	24	21	18	12	10	7	7
Insurance Ancillary Services	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Insurance Managers	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0
Insurance Society	3	3	3	3	2	1	1	1	0	0
TOTAL	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	161	165	166	168	163	163	155	147	154	161

Source: CBB- Insurance Market Review 2012).

Takaful and Conventional Insurance:

The basic idea of an insurance agreement is that it is a mutual co-operation between two parties to protect one of them from unexpected future financial loss. Under conventional setup the main viewpoint of insurance is to minimize the risk. Pfeffer (1956) defines as “insurance is a device for the reduction of risk of one party, called the insured, through the transfer of particular risks to another party, called the insurer, who offers a restoration, at least in part, of economic losses suffered by the insured”.

There are many conceptual and operational differences between these two types of insurances; the Islamic Insurance and the Conventional Insurance.

Takaful (THE ISLAMIC INSURANCE)

Takaful system (Islamic insurance) is well-known as a model of mutual cooperation (*ta’awun*) and donation (*tabarru’*), where the mutual protection of the members is guaranteed through risk sharing collectively and voluntarily by the group of participants. (Dusuki, 2011; Redzuan et al., 2009). Basically, The term “*takaful*” was derived from the Arabic word *kafala*, that gives the meaning of ‘joint guarantee’ or ‘guaranteeing each other’. It can also be explained as a group of individuals who guarantees each other in opposition to potential loss or damage faced by anyone of group member. (Ahmad Musadik, 2010; Yusof T. O., Gbadamosi, A., & Hamadu, D, 2009).

Takaful can also be understood as a financial transaction of a mutual co-operation between two parties (individual member and rest of the members of the group) to provide a financial security to one member of the group against any misfortune (Ma’sum Billah, 2003).

In the holy Qur’an, in verse 5:2, ALLAH has ordered that: “... help you one another in *Al-Birr* and *At-Taqwa* (virtue, righteousness and piety); but do not help one another in sin and transgression ...”.

Conceptual and operational differences

Table 2: Conceptual differences

	Takaful	Conventional Insurance	Reference
Joint Guarantee/Taawun	involves a joint guarantee scheme in providing possible indemnity or contingency	based on compensation of loss in exchange of premium which is paid by insured	Billah, 2003a
	Participants mutually agree to help and guarantee each other by collecting contribution from individual, for the sake of mutual cooperation	insurance is worked on risk transferring process under which one protects themselves on behalf of others	(Maysami and Kwon 1999; Billah 2003a;
Social Solidarity/ Shared Responsibility	based on the idea of social solidarity, cooperation and joint indemnification of losses of the members.	loss is indemnified by the insurance company according to the terms and condition of the policy	(Maysami et al., 1997).
Concept of Aaqilah	based on the idea of <i>Aaqilah</i> for the payment of blood money wherein payment was made by the whole tribe. Islam accepted this principle of mutual compensation and joint liability	loss is indemnified by the insurance company according to the terms and condition of the policy	(Billah, 1998).
Risk Distribution	risk in Takaful is not exchanged by way of contribution payments made to operator which means operator is not selling and participant is not buying any risk coverage	Insurance is a contract between two parties, whereby first party agrees to undertake the risk of other party in exchange of premium and the other party promises to pay fixed sum of money to the first party on the happening of uncertain event with in a specific duration	(Omar and Dawood 2000). (Spence and Zeckhauser,1971).

Table 3: Operational differences

	Takaful	Conventional Insurance	Reference
Gharar	It is generally described as risk of loss or promise to pay money upon the happening of specified event.	conventional insurance system is totally based on the theory of risk taking and uncertainty	(El-Gamal, 2000).
Maisir or gambling	Maisir which is due to Gharar is also avoided under Takaful system	conventional insurance is regarded as a kind of gambling as the insured makes a bet on the loss occurrence and the same applies vice versa for the insurer	(Siddiqui 2000). (Khan, 2011).
Riba (Payment and collection of interest)	Money capital in Islamic finance is seen as on par with an enterprise which comes with both risks and rewards.	Conventional insurance companies normally place insurance funds in Riba/interest bearing instruments such as bond and loans.	(Siddiqui, 2004). (El.Gamal, 2001).
Investment of Funds	Takaful companies invest funds in interest free avenues and with the concept of Halal-o-Haram	Conventional insurers may invest in such type of assets that are strictly forbidden by the Shariah such as alcohol, gambling or pork are haram	(Ayub, 2003; Thanasegaran, 2008; Khan, 2011) , (Gait and Worthington, 2008).
Nature of Contract	Under Islamic law insurance transaction can not be concluded on this basis of buy and sale contract	contract is based on the principles of exchange of interest. The relationship is designed in such a way that the insured buys protection by payment of premium, and insurer provides protection against the insured risk.	(Ali, 2006).
Profit Distribution	every policyholder has the right to know how profits from different investments are divided among the participants	there is no hard and fast rule for profit distribution, it is totally depends on company management.	

Literature Review:

The question of the efficiency of the firms in insurance industry is very important in order to determine how the insurance industry will respond to various challenges and which firms are likely to survive (Berger et. al, 1993).

Cummins et al. (1996) calculated technical efficiency and productivity growth in the Italian insurance market by calculating approximately production frontiers based on a sample of 94 Italian insurers for the period 1985-1993. They concluded that there is 70-78 percent technical efficiency in the Italian insurance industry while, total factor productivity was found about 3.4 percent during the sample period. There was almost no change in efficiency on an average during the sample period. Though, productivity was declined with a cumulative decline of almost 25 percent throughout the sample period.

Fukuyama (1997) examined productive efficiency and productivity changes of Japanese life insurance companies by focusing primarily on the ownership structures (mutual and stock) and economic conditions (expansion and recession). He declared that productive efficiency and productivity

performances differ from time to time across the two ownership types under different economic conditions.

Rees and Kessner (2000) stated that the German firms has the average efficiency level of about 48 percent and British firms were marked at higher level of the average about 57 percent with median of 52 percent.

Abu Mansor and Radam (2000), in their research conducted to measure the productivity of the life insurance industry in Malaysia using the non-parametric Malmquist Index approach, stated that the overall productivity growth of the insurance industry in Malaysia was credited to both technical efficiency and technical progress. When they measured the efficiency performance, they evaluated the Malmquist Index of a sample of Malaysian insurance companies over the 1987 to 1997 period.

Noulas et al. (2001) examined the legal framework of insurance sector and the performance efficiency of the non-life insurance companies in Greece for the period of 1991-1996. They concluded that the insurance firms are not producing the projected effect and there is large difference amid insurance firms in respect of their efficiency level.

Cummins and Rubio-Misas (2001) conducted another study to know the effect of deregulation and consolidation on financial services markets by analyzing the Spanish insurance industry during the period of 1989-1998. They employed the data envelopment analysis (DEA) for estimating the "best practice" production and cost frontiers while the Malmquist index methodology was used to analyse factor productivity growth.

They stated that cost efficiency was comparatively low in the Spanish insurance market with an average of 22.7 percent in 1998 due to allocative inefficiency. It showed the failure to choose the optimal mix of inputs. They found Average allocative efficiency in 1998 was only 41.2 percent, while pure technical efficiency was on an average 60 percent. It shows that Spanish firms are comparatively more successful in employing technology than in choosing optimal inputs.

Diacon et al. (2002) made a comparison was amongst insurance companies in the U.K., Spain, Sweden and Denmark. He concluded that U.K. insurers are particularly at low levels of scale with mix efficiencies.

Cummins et al. (2004) analysed Spanish stock and mutual insurers throughout the period 1989-1997 and examined the effects of organizational structure on efficiency. The outputs show that stocks and mutuals represent distinct technologies as they are being operated on separate production, cost, and revenue.

Tone and Sahoo (2005) used a new variant of DEA model to examine the performance of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India. The findings show a significant heterogeneity in the cost efficiency scores over the course of 19 years. A decline in performance after 1994-1995 can be taken as evidence of increasing allocative inefficiencies arising from the huge initial fixed cost undertaken by LIC in modernizing its operations. A significant increase in cost efficiency in 2000-2001 is, however, cause for optimism that LIC may now be realizing a benefit from such modernization. This will stand them in good stead in terms of future competition. Results from a sensitivity analysis are in broad agreement with the main findings of this study.

Hao and Chou (2005) estimated the Translog cost function for 16 Taiwan life insurance companies over the period of 1977-1999. They applied the distribution free approach (DFA) and Battese and Coelli (DFP) model to estimate inefficiency. Because of the market share, diversification of the product strategy, scale efficiency (SE), and market growth ration, the authors tested the constants or residuals to find out whether are related to the so-called X-efficiencies.

Weiss and Choi (2008) investigated the impact of regulation on state automobile insurance markets while controlling for other state insurance market characteristics that may be related to performance. The results suggest that insurers in competitive and non-stringently regulated states may benefit from market power by charging higher unit prices, however insurers in these states are on average more cost X efficient and cost X-efficient insurers charge lower prices and earn smaller profits. The empirical results also suggest that insurers in some rate regulated states are less revenue and cost-scale efficient than in competitive states.

Cummins and Xie (2008) analyzed the productivity and efficiency effects of mergers and acquisitions (M&As) in the US property-liability insurance industry during the period 1994-2003 using DEA and Malmquist productivity indices. They wanted to determine whether M&As are value-enhancing, value-neutral, or value-reducing. The analysis examines efficiency and productivity change for acquirers, acquisition targets, and non-M&A firms. They also examined the firm characteristics associated with becoming an acquirer or target through probit analysis. The results provide evidence that M&As in property-liability insurance were value-enhancing.

Acquiring firms achieved more revenue efficiency gains than non-acquiring firms, and target firms experienced greater cost and allocative efficiency growth than non-targets. Factors other than efficiency enhancement are important factors in property-liability insurer M&As. Financially, vulnerable insurers are significantly more likely to become acquisition targets, consistent with corporate control theory, and we also find evidence that M&As are motivated to achieve diversification. However, there is no evidence that scale economies played an important role in the insurance M&A wave.

Chen et al. (2009) evaluate the efficiency of life insurers operating in China and compare foreign firms with domestic firms. They find that foreign insurers have not brought efficiency into the Chinese market, and that the market is still dominated by domestic giants. However, the gap between foreign insurers and domestic insurers is narrowing.

Dutta and Sengupta (2010) tested the impact on efficiency changes due to increasing investment on IT-infrastructure which is leading to technological innovation in business operation of the private companies. They stated that increasing investment on IT-infrastructure has significant positive impact on scale and technical efficiency change under constant and variable returns to scale assumptions.

Eling and Luhnen (2010) inspected the efficiency of 3,831 companies from 91 countries using DEA and SFA techniques. They selected the sample of 28 firm of life insurance companies and 113 firms of non-life insurance companies from Malaysia.

Methods Of Measuring Insurance Performance Efficiency

The methods used to measure the performance efficiency can be divided into two categories named as parametric and non-parametric. The Stochastic Frontier Approach (composed error), Distribution Free Approach (different composed error) and the Thick Frontier Approach come under the parametric approaches. while, the Data Envelopment Analysis and the Free Disposable Hull (FDH) are the forms of parametric approaches [Cummins et al. (1999); Cummins and Zi (1998)].

Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) are the two main methods from the above that have been widely used in the literature to measure the efficiency of the insurance industry.

Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA), also known as the Econometric Frontier Approach was developed by Aigner et al., (1977). This is the method that stipulates functional form for cost, profit or production relationship among inputs, outputs, and environmental factors and permits for random error (Berger and Humphrey, 1997). The functions are used to estimate the distance that a firm is from the optimizing envelope (Seale, 2000).

Charnes et al. (1978) developed a method, known as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) or the mathematical programming, draws upon the efficiency concept in Farrell (1957).

Charnes et al. (1978) states that DEA calculates approximately the efficiency under the assumption of constant returns to scale. This method builds the frontier of the observed input-output ratios by linear programming. It presumes that linear substitution is possible between observed input combinations on an isoquant. In other words, DEA is a model that mingles all the input and output information on the firm into a single measure of productive efficiency that lies between zero (i.e. a completely inefficient firm) and unity (i.e. a completely efficient firm). Additionally, the DEA effectively approximates the frontier by finding a set of linear estimates that bound (envelop) the observed data (Leong et al., 2003). As a result, this method is a benchmarking method in the sense that the 'best practice' firms lie on the frontier and 'envelop' other inefficient firms (Neal, 2004).

Table 4: Summary Of Studies On Insurance Efficiencies That Used The DEA.

Sr. No		
1	Cummins et al. (1996)	<i>Productivity and Technical efficiency in the Italian Insurance Industry</i> . Working Paper Series. The Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania.
2	Berger et al. (1997),	Efficiency of financial institutions: International survey and direction for future research. <i>European Journal of Operational Research</i> , 98: 175-212.
3	Fukuyama (1997)	Investigating Productive Efficiency and Productivity Changes of Japanese Life Insurance Companies", <i>Pacific-Basin Finance Journal</i> , 5 (4) September, pp.481-509
4	Cummins et al. (1999)	Consolidation and efficiency in the U.S. life insurance industry. <i>Journal of Banking & Finance</i> , 23: 325-357.
5	Cummins, Weiss, and Zi (1999)	Organizational Form and Efficiency: An Analysis of Stock and Mutual Property-Liability Insurers', <i>Management Science</i> , 45 (9) September, pp.1254-1269.
6	Meador et al. (2000)	Product Focus Versus Diversification: Estimates of X-Efficiency for the U.S. Life Insurance Industry," in P. T. Harker and S. A.
7	Rees and Kessner (2000)	Regulation and efficiency in European insurance markets, <i>Economic Policy</i> , 29, Centre for Economic Policy Research, London.
8	Cummins and Rubio-Misas (2001)	Deregulation, consolidation, and efficiency: evidence from the spanish industry, <i>Working Paper Series</i> , The Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania.
9	Diacon et al. (2002)	Size and efficiency in European long-term insurance companies: an international comparison. <i>The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance</i> , 27 (3): 444-466.
10	Khalid et al. (2012)	"Analyzing the technical efficiency of insurance companies in GCC," <i>The Journal of Risk Finance</i> , Vol. 13 No. 4, 2012 pp. 362-380

Table 5: Insurance Firms Included For Performance Analysis

The Following insurance firms were included for performance analysis from conventional and Takaful Insurance.

Sr. No	Conventional Insurance Firms	Sr. No	Takaful Insurance Firms
1	Al Ahlia Ins.	1	Chartis Takaful -
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	2	Legal & General Gulf Takaful
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	3	Solidarity Family Takaful
4	Bahrain National Insurance	4	Solidarity General Takaful
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	5	International Takaful
6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	6	T'azur Company
7	Legal & General Gulf		
8	Life Insurance Corporation International		
9	Med. & Gulf		

10	Saudi National Insurance Co		
11	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co.		
12	United Insurance		

Source: (CBC- Insurance Market Review 2010 & 2012)

Research Methodology and data Analysis

The present research study uses the DEA to evaluate the efficiency of insurance industry in Bahrain. The efficiency-change component has been calculated relative to constant-returns-to-scale technology and a pure efficiency component has been calculated relative to the variable returns to scale (VRS) technology. The scale-efficiency change component has also been calculated which captures changes in the deviation between the VRS and constant-returns-to-scale (CRS) technology. The subset of pure efficiency change examines the relative ability of operators to convert inputs into outputs, while scale efficiency measures the extent to which the operators can take advantage of returns to scale, by altering its size in the direction of the optimal scale.

Table 6: Performance of Insurance Firms:

Conventional Insurance Firms			Takaful Firms	
	2011 (BD in millions)	2012 (BD in millions)	2011 (BD in millions)	2012 (BD in millions)
Total Assets	1,135.96	1,242.93	114.04	114.75
Total Liabilities	714.16	784.43	65.79	75.88
Insurers' paid-up Capital	110.94	118.81	62.67	55.13
The net investment income	22.69	25.90	0.057	0.678

From the above table, it is clear that total assets of Conventional Insurers was BD 1,242.93 million in 2012 compared to BD 1,135.96 million in 2011. It has shown an increase by almost 9%. While Total assets of Takaful Firms (including both Shareholders Fund and Participants Funds), according to the Insurance Firms Returns (IFR) submitted by Takaful Firms registered BD 114.75 million in 2012 compared to BD 114.04 million in 2011.

Total liabilities of Conventional Insurers as shown in the table has increased around 10%. As it was BD 784.43 million in 2012 compared to BD 714.16 million in 2011. Total liabilities of Takaful Firms accounted for BD 75.88 million in 2012 compared to BD 65.79 million in 2011. It shows an increase of almost 15%.

Conventional Insurers' paid-up capital registered BD 118.81 million in 2012 compared to BD 110.94 million in 2011, registering an increase of around 7%. The Takaful Firms accounted Eligible Paid-up Capital registered BD 55.13 million in 2012 while it was BD 62.67 million in 2011.

Conventional Insurers' net investment income (investment income less investment cost) increased by around 14% that registered BD 25.90 million in 2012 compared to BD 22.69 million in 2011. On the other hand, Net investment income of Participants Funds of Takaful Firms increased significantly to register BD 678,000 in 2012 compared to BD 57,000 in 2011.

Takaful's Gross Contributions for the year 2012:

The Takaful industry in Bahrain has experienced a remarkable growth in terms of gross contributions in the last ten years. By the end of 2012, there were 7 locally incorporated Takaful firms in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The Takaful Firms' gross contributions represent around 22% of the total Bahrain gross

premiums/contributions in 2012 to register BD 53.67 million compared to BD 43.91 million, an increase of around 22% over the previous year.(CBC- Insurance Market Review 2012).

Long-term Insurance coverage includes the following policies:

- Group life assurance;
- Group credit life assurance;
- Level and decreasing term assurance;
- Unit-linked assurance;
- Participating with profit policies; and
- Children’s education policies.

Figure 1: Five Year Performance : Gross Premiums & Claims of Long-term Insurance

Table 7: Changes in gross premium and Gross claims

Year	Gross Premiums (BD '000)	Gross Claims (BD '000)
2008	51,572	21,511
2009	57,310	13,847
2010	51,356	18,843
2011	52,591	20,180
2012	60,159	21,892

Source: (CBC- Insurance Market Review 2012).

Figure 2: Changes in gross premium and Gross claims

The above table and Graph show that there has been a significant increase in Gross premium during last five years. Gross premium in 2008 was BD 51,572,000 while it was BD 60,159,000 in 2012. It shows a increase of almost 17% in gross premium from 2008 to 2012.

On the other hand, Gross Claims in 2008 was BD 2, 15, 11,000 while in 2012, it was BD 2, 18, 92,000. It has also increased by almost 2%. It shows that the premium that is the output for the company has increased with higher percentage (17%) than that of increase in input i.e. claims 2%. It indicates towards the increasing profitability of insurance Industry in Bahrain.

Production frontier and efficiency:

Since the basic components of the Malmquist productivity index are related to measures of efficiency, the study initially reports efficiency change for the 18 firms in Bahrain from 2009-2012 in Tables 8 and 9 under CRS and VRS, respectively.

The values of unity mean that the firm is on the industry frontier in the related year, while the values less than unity mean that the firm is below the frontier or technically inefficient. as a result, the lower the values from unity, the more inefficient it is compared to the values closer to unity

Efficiency of the Takaful and Conventional Insurance Companies, 2009-2012

Table 8: Constant Returns to Scale

Sr.No	Conventional Insurance Company	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	Al Ahlia Ins.	0.692	0.7129	0.5763	0.5224
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	0.8296	0.7512	0.7911	0.7861
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	0.6154	0.6163	0.6349	0.5783
4	Bahrain National Insurance	0.6847	0.6247	0.609	0.5831
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	0.6622	0.5963	0.6811	0.6738
6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	0.6838	0.6792	0.6896	0.7415
7	Legal & General Gulf	0.1014	0.5629	0.7932	0.4798
8	Life Insurance Corporation International	1	0.9844	1	0.9441
9	Med. & Gulf_2009	1	0.7923	0.4174	0.453
10	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	1	0.7364	0.5667	0.5517
11	Saudi National Insurance Co	0.8927	0.6683	0.7056	0.6735
12	United Insurance	0.7739	0.7947	0.8884	0.7014

	Geomean	0.6664	0.7021	0.6798	0.6271
Sr.No	Takaful Company	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	Chartis Takaful	0.3732	0.3792	1	0.6679
2	International Takaful	0.4312	0.4243	0.4224	0.3644
3	Legal & General Gulf Takaful	1	1	0.951	0.4247
4	Solidarity Family Takaful	0.6507	0.5526	0.3726	1
5	Solidarity General Takaful	0.5019	0.4919	0.4982	0.5389
6	T'azur Company	0.9148	0.7385	0.3418	0.3404
	Geomean	0.602996	0.564319	0.542475	0.51637
	Overall Geomean	0.644565	0.652765	0.63054	0.587789

For the years reported in Tables 8 and 9, Life Insurance Corporation International was consistently efficient, both under CRS and VR). Axa Ins. (Gulf) was consistently efficient under VRS but not under CRS. International Takaful was the least efficient firm for CRS and VRS.

As indicated by the weighted geometric mean in Tables 8 and 9, the average efficiency for the whole industry reduced for the period 2009 to 2012 but showed a slight increase in 2010. On average, efficiency performance of Bahrain's insurance industry was relatively higher based on VRS than on CRS.

Table 9: Variable Return to scale

Variable Return to scale					
Sr.No	Conventional Insurance Company	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	Al Ahlia Ins.	0.76523	0.82139	0.64912	0.56961
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	1	0.94557	1	1
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	0.77866	0.76453	0.78953	0.7254
4	Bahrain National Insurance	0.81965	0.78396	0.77207	0.71619
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	0.72496	0.66687	0.74824	0.74197
6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	0.75624	0.75387	0.7693	0.81794
7	Legal & General Gulf	0.10138	0.64347	1	0.55449
8	Life Insurance Corporation International	1	0.98439	1	1
9	Med. & Gulf_2009	1	0.86136	0.49337	0.50758
10	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	1	0.80982	0.69415	0.67241
11	Saudi National Insurance Co	1	0.76931	0.84245	0.81516
12	United Insurance	0.95406	1	1	0.86112
	Geomean	0.73752	0.80981	0.79702	0.73249
Sr.No.	Takaful Company	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	Chartis Takaful	0.39856	0.39155	1	0.71107
2	International Takaful	0.57344	0.57668	0.59056	0.49256
3	Legal & General Gulf Takaful	1	1	1	0.46026
4	Solidarity Family Takaful	0.73214	0.62001	0.37353	1

5	Solidarity General Takaful	0.56758	0.62184	0.63276	0.6491
6	T'azur Company	1	0.9883	0.52576	0.42215
	Geomean	0.67546	0.664427	0.647045	0.594554
	Overall Geomean	0.716223	0.758123	0.743520	0.683279

Productivity performance of individual company

Tables 10 to 12 report the performance of the firms from 2009 to 2012 in terms of TFP change and its two subcomponents, technical change and efficiency change, respectively. Note that a value of the Malmquist TFP productivity index and its components of less than unity mean a decrease or decline in productivity. on the other hand, values greater than unity indicate improvements of productivity in the relevant aspect.

Table 10: Insurance Firms Relative Malmquist TFP Change between Time Period t and t + 1, 2009-2012

	Conventional Insurance Company	2009-2010	2010-2011	2011-2012	Mean
1	Al Ahlia Ins.	0.873766	1.452993	1.034237	1.120332
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	0.990671	0.943403	1.058893	0.997656
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	1.034459	0.992015	1.062326	1.0296
4	Bahrain National Insurance	1.010517	1.045322	1.096676	1.050838
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	1.016077	0.944871	1.003604	0.988184
6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	0.989323	0.976255	0.993682	0.98642
7	Legal & General Gulf	0.398327	0.688543	0.986881	0.69125
8	Life Insurance Corporation International	0.986795	0.977986	1.071687	1.012156
9	Med. & Gulf	3.401394	2.167278	1.010063	2.192912
10	Saudi National Insurance Co	1.289576	0.813852	0.910829	1.004752
11	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co.	78310.42	1.007603	1.002929	26104.14
12	United Insurance	0.93526	0.979719	1.141438	1.018806
	Mean	6526.946	1.082487	1.031104	2176.353
	Takaful Company	2009-2010	2010-2011	2011-2012	Mean
13	Chartis Takaful -	0.901151	0.311501	2.885118	1.365923
14	Legal & General Gulf Takaful	131250	0.87478	1.012989	43750.63
15	Solidarity Family Takaful	1.14993	1.319995	7.5506	0.823311
16	Solidarity General Takaful	0.911242	1.006555	1.000666	0.972821
17	International Takaful	1.015301	1.023838	1.090106	1.043081
18	T'azur Company	0.775641	2.105745	0.746893	1.209426
	Mean	21875.79	1.107069	1.12263	7292.674
	Overall Geomean	13.81918	1.000727	0.513168	10.8755

Table 10 displays calculated changes in the Malmquist-based Total Factor Productivity index. As evidenced in the results, Al Ahlia Ins., Bahrain National Insurance, Med. & Gulf, Saudi Insurance

Arabian Co., International Takaful, Solidarity Family Takaful and Legal & General Gulf had positive productivity changes for adjacent years of 2009-2010, 2010-2011 and 2011-2012. In contrast, Med. & Gulf recorded deterioration in TFP for the years 2009-2012.

The Malmquist TFP index is further decomposed into its two components, technical change and efficiency change. The results of technical change and efficiency change are reported in Tables 11 and 12.

Table 11: Insurance Firms Relative Technical Change between Time Period t and $t + 1$,

2009-2012

Table 11 presents the index values of technical progress/regress as measured by average shifts in the best-practice frontier from period t to $t+1$. According to the results Al Ahlia Ins., Axa Ins. (Gulf), Bahrain National Insurance, Bahrain National Life Assurance, Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance and Solidarity Family Takaful are the firms that experienced technical progress from year 2009-2010 to 2011-2012, while the other firms experienced both technical progress and regress.

Conventional Insurance Company	2009-2010	2010-2011	2011-2012	Mean
Al Ahlia Ins.	0.9992563	0.996251	1.0015122	0.999007
Axa Ins. (Gulf)	0.9992719	1.0007287	1	1
Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	1.0028121	1.0019434	0.9911012	0.998619
Bahrain National Insurance	0.9949573	0.9986264	1.0015636	0.998382
Bahrain National Life Assurance	0.9968901	1.0047218	1.0005398	1.000717
Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	1.0000799	1.0002145	1.000757	1.00035
Legal & General Gulf	0.9095898	1.1182763	0.9650031	0.997623
Life Insurance Corporation International	1	1	1	1
Med. & Gulf_2009	0.9982292	0.9783392	0.988058	0.988209
Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	0.9989133	0.981356	0.9972114	0.992494
Saudi National Insurance Co	0.9887693	1.0057484	0.9990564	0.997858
United Insurance	1.0008092	1	0.9971456	0.999318
Mean	0.9907982	1.0071838	0.9951624	0.997715
Takaful Company				
Chartis Takaful	0.9849715	1.078013	0.9610716	1.008019
International Takaful	1.0089759	1.0090797	0.9848065	1.000954
Legal & General Gulf Takaful	1	1	0.9580945	0.986031
Solidarity Family Takaful	0.9952145	0.9885262	1.0231604	1.0023
Solidarity General Takaful	1.0896306	0.9876473	1.0247643	1.034014
T'azur Company	0.9982616	0.8475305	1.1169219	0.987571
Mean	1.0128424	0.9851328	1.0114699	1.003148
Overall Geomean	1.0095607	0.9875733	1.0088618	1.002002

Table 12: Changes in Firms Relative Efficiency between Time Period t and $t + 1$,

2009-2012

Conventional Insurance Company	2009-2010	2010-2011	2011-2012	Mean
Al Ahlia Ins.	0.93094	1.260642	1.141317	1.110966
Axa Ins. (Gulf)	1.056794	0.946258	1	1.001017
Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	1.021347	0.970212	1.083145	1.024902
Bahrain National Insurance	1.040257	1.014002	1.07971	1.044657
Bahrain National Life Assurance	1.083723	0.895454	1.008998	0.996058
Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	1.003225	0.980152	0.941244	0.974874
Legal & General Gulf	1	1	2.081642	1.360547
Life Insurance Corporation International	1.015855	0.984392	1	1.000082
Med. & Gulf_2009	1.158903	1.708045	0.960401	1.275783
Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	1.233504	1.14489	1.029453	1.135949
Saudi National Insurance Co	1.285273	0.918428	1.032506	1.078736
United Insurance	0.95483	1	1.15796	1.037597
Mean	1.065388	1.06854	1.126365	1.086764
Takaful Company				
Chartis Takaful	1.002614	0.422096	1.351585	0.925432
International Takaful	1.0033	0.985354	1.180765	1.056473
Legal & General Gulf Takaful	1	1	2.081642	1.360547
Solidarity Family Takaful	1.175203	1.640825	0.382177	1.066068
Solidarity General Takaful	0.994543	0.970613	0.998961	0.988039
T'azur Company	1.010084	1.593155	1.391049	1.331429
Mean	1.030957	1.102007	1.23103	1.121331
Overall Geomean	1.049964443	1.036956534	1.099373235	1.090554672

Table 12 displays changes in relative efficiency for each individual company. The results indicate considerable variation across companies and times. Only four firms (Bahrain National Insurance, Legal & General Gulf, Saudi Insurance Arabian Co and Tazur Company) were found to be efficient (and therefore showed no change in efficiency) in all periods from 2009-2012. For the other firms, there were periods with positive, negative or no changes in efficiency.

In order to identify a change in scale efficiency, the efficiency change is further decomposed into two subcomponents, namely pure efficiency change (PEch) and scale efficiency change (SEch), the results of which are reported in Table 13.

Table 13: Changes in Efficiency Components by Firms between Time Period t and $t + 1$, 2009-2012

Sr.No	Insurance firm	2009-2010		2010-2011		2011-2012	
		PEFch	SEFch	PEFch	SEFch	PEFch	SEFch
1	Conventional Insurance Company Al Ahlia Ins.	1.073383	0.959752	0.790273	1.023006	0.877506282	1.0330705
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	0.945569	0.957655	1.057564	0.995852	1	0.9936599
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	0.981853	1.019965	1.032705	0.997487	0.918765903	0.9914283
4	Bahrain National Insurance	0.956453	0.953975	0.984836	0.989853	0.927621942	1.0321801
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	0.919875	0.978845	1.122025	1.018038	0.991616371	0.9975809

6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	0.996865	0.996423	1.020469	0.994969	1.063227938	1.0112288
7	Legal & General Gulf	6.346965	0.874741	1.554079	0.906796	0.554485	1.0908701
8	Life Insurance Corporation International	0.984393	1	1.015854	1	1	0.944059
9	Med. & Gulf_2009	0.861357	0.91977	0.572783	0.919783	1.028795774	1.0550391
10	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	0.809818	0.909371	0.857162	0.897797	0.968680895	1.0048804
11	Saudi National Insurance Co	0.769307	0.973088	1.095075	0.964201	0.967603974	0.9864555
12	United Insurance	1.048154	0.979738	1	1.117856	0.861123	0.9168388
13	Chartis Takaful	0.982404	1.03443	2.553952	1.032481	0.711107	0.9393576
14	International Takaful	1.005657	0.978418	1.024078	0.972122	0.834041696	1.0343656
15	Legal & General Gulf Takaful	1	1	1	0.950952	0.460259	0.97022
16	Solidarity Family Takaful	0.846845	1.002918	0.602456	1.119191	2.677189807	1.0024099
17	Solidarity General Takaful	1.09561	0.894507	1.017549	0.995371	1.025829862	1.054451
18	T'azur Company	0.988296	0.816766	0.531982	0.870074	0.802935202	1.2402274

Note: PEch = Pure Efficiency Change, and SEch = Scale Efficiency Change

The results explain that the pure efficiency and scale efficiency come out to be equally important sources of growth to efficiency change. Legal & General Gulf Takaful recorded no changes in annual growth for both the scale and pure efficiencies during the period 2009-2010 to 2010-2011. While it was decreased in 2011-2012. Relative to other insurance firms, Legal & General Gulf recorded the highest deterioration of pure efficiency from 2009-2010- to 2011-2012.

Productivity performance of the industry

Table 14 summarizes the performance of Malmquist productivity index of the insurance industry in Bahrain between 2009-2012. On average, International Takaful recorded the highest growth in TFP followed by Saudi National Insurance Co and Med. & Gulf_2009 at 2nd and 3rd place respectively. While in technical changes Solidarity General Takaful recorded the highest growth followed by Chartis Takaful and Solidarity Family Takaful at 2nd and 3rd place respectively. Furthermore, the efficiency change is largely contributed by Legal & General Gulf and Legal & General Gulf Takaful jointly.

Table 14: Summary of Malmquist Productivity Index of Insurance Firms

Sr.No	Conventional Insurance Company	TFPch	EFFch	TECch	PEch	SEch
1	Al Ahlia Ins.	1.120332	1.110966	0.999007	0.906276391	1.004745
2	Axa Ins. (Gulf)	0.997656	1.001017	1	1	0.982231
3	Bahrain Kuwait Insurance	1.0296	1.024902	0.998619	0.976658235	1.002885
4	Bahrain National Insurance	1.050838	1.044657	0.998382	0.956018398	0.991489
5	Bahrain National Life Assurance	0.988184	0.996058	1.000717	1.007763043	0.998027
6	Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance	0.98642	0.974874	1.00035	1.026488691	1.000847
7	Legal & General Gulf	0.69125	1.360547	0.997623	1.76187996	0.952915
8	Life Insurance Corporation International	1.012156	1.000082	1	1	0.980994
9	Med. & Gulf_2009	2.192912	1.275783	0.988209	0.797690213	0.962818
10	Saudi Insurance Arabian Co	1.004752	1.135949	0.992494	0.876079755	0.936148
11	Saudi National Insurance Co	26104.14	1.078736	0.997858	0.93414384	0.974539
12	United Insurance	1.018806	1.037597	0.999318	0.966414574	1.001374
13	Chartis Takaful	1.365923	0.925432	1.008019	1.212844507	1.001086

14	International Takaful	43750.63	1.056473	1.000954	0.950583296	0.99458
15	Legal & General Gulf Takaful	0.823311	1.360547	0.986031	0.772089115	0.973516
16	Solidarity Family Takaful	0.972821	1.066068	1.0023	1.109522917	1.040092
17	Solidarity General Takaful	1.043081	0.988039	1.034014	1.045752569	0.979186
18	T'azur Company	1.209426	1.331429	0.987571	0.750161743	0.958779

Note: *TFPch* = Total Factor Productivity Change; *EFFch* = Efficiency Change; *TECch* = Technical Change; *PEch* = Pure Efficiency Change; and *SEch* = Scale Efficiency Change

The efficiency change in terms of scale efficiency and pure efficiency analysed and was found that pure efficiency was higher rather than the scale efficiency. This indicates that the size of the companies plays an important role in affecting efficiency changes. On average, the insurance firms have been found experiencing technical progress.

Conclusion

Overall, Axa Ins. (Gulf), Bahrain National Life Assurance, Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance, Legal & General Gulf, Legal & General Gulf Takaful, and Solidarity Family Takaful have been found to be below average in TFP but slightly above average or equal to average for technical change (TECch). However, in the case of efficiency, Bahrain National Life Assurance, Gulf Union Insurance & Reinsurance, Chartis Takaful, and Solidarity General Takaful were found below average. While in case of pure efficiency change, Al Ahlia Ins., Bahrain Kuwait Insurance, Bahrain National Insurance, Med. & Gulf_2009, Saudi Insurance Arabian Co, Saudi National Insurance Co, United Insurance, International Takaful, Legal & General Gulf Takaful and T'azur Company were below average.

The analysis shows that some companies are below average in Efficiency or pure efficiency but they have equalled the industry average scale efficiency change or in technical Efficiency change. It shows that if a company is weaker in one parameter at one side then on the other, it is stronger in other parameter of efficiency. Overall efficiency analysis shows that most of the takaful firms are stronger in Efficiency and Technical efficiency change in comparison to conventional insurance firms. One way for weaker firms to improve their efficiency is through increasing the company size either by increasing their customer base and market share, or through merging with other *takaful/conventional firms*.

It is expected that takaful companies will improve the scale efficiency and then they would be in a better position to gain competitive advantage over its counterparts i.e. conventional insurance firms. As there were only six *takaful* companies included in the analysis, the findings may only be limited to these firms in Bahrain only. The result may not be investigative to other firms in some other country. Therefore, it is recommended to test the generaliseability of the result in some other country and scenario with some different insurance firms. A comprehensive study may be conducted to test the efficiency of insurance industry with inclusion of some new established takaful and conventional insurance firms in Bahrain.

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